

The Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Adherence to Taking Medication in Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients at the Same Community Health Center Timor-Leste

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 04 June 2025	Background: Pulmonary tuberculosis (pulmonary TB) is an infectious disease that is still a global health problem. The success of its treatment is highly dependent on patient compliance in taking medication, but non-compliance still often occurs, risking therapy failure. One factor that influences compliance is patient self-efficacy in completing treatment. This study aims to analyze the relationship between self-efficacy and medication compliance in pulmonary TB patients at the Same Health Center. Method: This study used an analytical observational design with a cross-sectional approach in 34 pulmonary TB patients at the Same Health Center who were selected by purposive sampling. Data were collected through a self-efficacy questionnaire and the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) to assess medication compliance. Analysis was carried out using the Spearman Rank correlation test. This study has received ethical approval number 14 / EC-LPPM / UWHS / II-2025. Results: there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and medication compliance in pulmonary TB patients with a result of 0.000 (≤ 0.05). Patients with high levels of self-efficacy tend to be more compliant in undergoing drug therapy than patients with low self-efficacy. Conclusion: Self-efficacy has a significant relationship with medication adherence in pulmonary TB patients. Therefore, interventions aimed at improving patient self-efficacy need to be implemented in pulmonary TB management strategies to improve the success of therapy
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A. INTRODUCTION

Pulmonary tuberculosis is a type of infectious disease caused by the bacterium *Mycobacterium Pulmonary TB*. Tuberculosis can attack various body tissues and/or organs, but mostly occurs in the lungs [1]. Pulmonary tuberculosis or better known by the public as pulmonary TB is not a new disease, but has existed since ancient times. However, even though pulmonary TB is not a new type of disease, in reality the number of pulmonary TB cases is still relatively high and continues to be a world problem. So the WHO (World Health Organization) in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program announced the 'End Pulmonary TB' strategy which aims to end the pulmonary TB epidemic in the world.

In 2021, around 10.6 million people were diagnosed with pulmonary TB worldwide, which is higher than 10 million cases in 2020 (WHO, 2023). Based on the 2021

Global TB Report, Indonesia has 824,000 cases of pulmonary TB, placing it in third place after India and China. At the national level, Riskesdas 2018 reported that pulmonary TB is the second deadliest infectious disease in the world after COVID-19 and the 13th cause of death.

This TB problem also affects Timor-Leste, which has a high prevalence. Preliminary studies at Community Health Centers show that patient self-efficacy greatly influences their compliance with TB treatment. Patients with low efficacy often do not complete therapy, which worsens treatment and prolongs transmission. This is due to a lack of education and awareness of the importance of completing treatment. Handling the high prevalence of pulmonary TB must be done to control pulmonary TB disease, one of which is through treatment. Treatment for pulmonary TB can be carried out for six to nine months and is given in two stages, namely the initial stage and then the

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advanced stage. The long duration of treatment can cause feelings of boredom, anxiety, depression, isolation, rejection, feelings of uselessness because you may lose your job, no longer be able to be socially active, and even lose hope that you will recover and be able to carry out your activities as before [2].

The solution to increasing compliance with pulmonary TB treatment begins with increasing education. Counseling at Community Health Centers needs to provide in-depth explanations about the importance of completing TB treatment, especially for patients with low levels of self-efficacy. This education is expected to increase patient understanding and motivation. In addition, psychosocial assistance through family and community support has proven to be effective in strengthening patient self-efficacy. Emotional and social support is very helpful in reducing the psychological barriers that patients often experience during treatment. The final step is ongoing monitoring to ensure patient compliance with treatment. This monitoring can be carried out through regular visits by health workers or with the help of technology-based applications that make remote monitoring easier. This ongoing monitoring can prevent treatment discontinuation, which is often the cause of therapy failure. By implementing these three solutions, it is hoped that the success of pulmonary TB treatment can increase, and the risk of disease transmission can be reduced significantly.

Individual self-efficacy can influence patient compliance with treatment, and patient non-compliance with treatment is the main cause of treatment failure and relapse. According to Bandura in (Alwisol, 2018). Self-efficacy is the final result of a cognitive process related to an individual's comfort in doing something that influences motivation, thought processes and emotional conditions. with good self-efficacy, patients have motivation and can also look for solutions if during the treatment process they feel bored because the treatment takes a long time and will complete the treatment until they recover [2].

Low patient self-efficacy will result in treatment failure. Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in managing certain behaviors in order to obtain healing. The patient's self-confidence to recover is achieved partly from the cognitive or knowledge provided by health workers through counseling. In a preliminary study conducted by Kustriyani (2020) In the Surabaya city area, the information obtained was that patients said they were bored, fed up with their illness and felt they were a burden on their families, there were also those who said it was difficult to carry out daily activities because of the pain they were suffering from, some patients were also reluctant to come to the clinic on the grounds that they were tired of treatment. This is due to a lack of self-efficacy in patients (Kustriyani, 2020).

The patient's self-efficacy or self-confidence must be ensured to be in good condition because this can change behavior to achieve healing. Self-efficacy can influence

individuals in determining the actions they will take to achieve their goals. The better a person's self-efficacy, the better the way of thinking and actions chosen in achieving goals. However, the lower a person's self-efficacy, the less good the way of thinking and actions they choose to achieve their goals. Pulmonary TB sufferers must have high self-efficacy to achieve recovery, because low self-efficacy of sufferers will result in treatment failure. Factors that influence self-efficacy include the nature of the task at hand, external intensity, and also information about one's abilities. One of the factors that influences self-efficacy is external intensive that can be obtained from patient supporter (PS)[4].

The self-efficacy of pulmonary TB patients can be caused by the length of time the patient has suffered from TB. This is because prolonged TB can cause a general decline in physical health, such as weight loss, fatigue and respiratory problems. This can affect a person's self-efficacy because they may feel weak or unable to carry out activities as usual. People who suffer from TB may experience social stigma because the disease is often thought to be contagious or associated with certain conditions (for example, poverty or poor environmental conditions). This stigma can reduce their self-efficacy because they feel judged or isolated by society [5].

Data from the Same Health Center in May 2024 numbered 38 people. The results of a preliminary study conducted by researchers on 5 patients found that 3 patients who were compliant with taking medication for pulmonary TB disease were bored with taking the medication. This was also explained by the patient being bored of taking the medication according to the doctor's instructions. The patient also said that he was no longer enthusiastic about his illness, the patient also closed himself off and was reluctant to socialize with local residents. Because of the impact of medication adherence and the level of self-efficacy on TB patients, the researchers were interested in conducting research with the title "The relationship between medication adherence and the self-efficacy of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center." The aim of this research is to determine the relationship between medication adherence and the self-efficacy of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center.

B. METHODS

This study used a quantitative design with a cross-sectional approach which aimed to determine the relationship between self-efficacy and medication adherence in pulmonary TB patients. This research was carried out using a purposive sampling method, where respondents were selected based on inclusion criteria, namely pulmonary TB patients who were undergoing treatment, aged ≥ 18 years, and able to communicate verbally.

The instruments used in this research consisted of a

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respondent characteristics questionnaire and a self-efficacy questionnaire. The respondent characteristics questionnaire includes information regarding name (initials), gender, age, education level, and medication adherence. Meanwhile, self-efficacy was measured using a questionnaire adapted from Noviani's (2018) research, whose validity had been tested with a correlation value of $r = 0.779-0.892$, greater than the r table (0.765), so it was declared valid. The instrument reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's Alpha, with results $\alpha > 0.765$, which shows that this instrument is reliable.

Compliance with taking medication in pulmonary TB patients was measured using the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS), with the following categories:

patients are said to be adherent if they get a score of 8, moderate compliance with a score of $6 - <8$, and low compliance with a score of <6 . Meanwhile, self-efficacy was measured using a Likert scale with three points, namely 3 for "able to do", 2 for "sometimes able", and 1 for "not able". Self-efficacy is categorized as good if the score is $\geq 75\%$ (≥ 56) and poor if $<75\%$ (<56).

Data analysis was carried out using statistical software, where univariate analysis was used to see the frequency distribution and percentage of each variable, while bivariate analysis was used to determine the relationship between self-efficacy and medication adherence in pulmonary TB patients.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Respondent Characteristics

a. Age

Table 4.1: Description of characteristics based on age of pulmonary TB patients at the same health center (n=34)

Karakteristik	(f)	(%)
Early adulthood: 26-35 years	13	38.2
Late adulthood: 36-45 years	5	14.7
Early elderly: 46-55 years	5	14.7
Late elderly: 56-65 years	7	20.6
Seniors: > 65 years	4	11.8
Total	34	100.0

Based on table 4.1, the largest age category of respondents in this study was early adulthood (26-35 years) with 13 respondents (38.2%). Meanwhile, the smallest age category of respondents was seniors (>65 years) with 4 respondents (11.8%). This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center are in the early adult age range, while the elderly age group has the least number of cases.

b. Gender

Table 4. 2 Description of characteristics of respondents based on gender of pulmonary TB patients at the same health center (n=34)

Gender	(n)	%
Man	23	67.6
Woman	11	32.4
Total	34	100.0

Based on table 4.2, it shows that the majority of respondents in this study were male, namely 23 respondents (67.6%). Meanwhile, there were 11 female respondents (32.4%). This indicates that cases of pulmonary TB at the Same Community Health Center are more experienced by men than women.

Table 4. 3 Description of Respondents' characteristics based on Education of Pulmonary TB Patients at the Same Community Health Center (n=34)

Education	(n)	%
Elementary school	7	20.6
Junior High School	5	14.7
Senior High School	8	23.5
College	14	41.2
Total	34	100.0

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Based on table 4.3, the highest educational category of respondents in this study was tertiary education (PT), with a total of 14 respondents (41.2%). Meanwhile, the lowest education category was junior high school, with 5 respondents (14.7%). This shows that the majority of

pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center have a higher level of education, namely tertiary education (PT), while the number of patients with junior high school education is relatively smaller.

c. Job

Table 4. 4 Description of Respondents' characteristics based on Occupation of Pulmonary TB Patients at the Same Community Health Center (n=34)

Job	(n)	%
Work	23	67.6
Doesn't work	11	32.4
Total	34	100.0

Based on table 4.4, the majority of respondents in this study were those who worked with 23 respondents (67.6%). Meanwhile, 11 respondents (32.4%) were unemployed. This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center come from groups who are actively working, while a small portion do not work.

In this sub-chapter, it is explained about the fulfillment of taking medication with the self-efficacy of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center and the results are as shown in the following table:

- a. Self-efficacy level of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center.

Table 4.5 Self-efficacy level of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center (n=34)

Self-efficacy	(n)	%
Poor self-efficacy	18	52.9
Good self-efficacy	16	47.1
Total	34	100.0

Based on table 4.5, the majority of respondents in this study had poor self-efficacy in adherence to taking medication, with a total of 18 respondents (52.9%). Meanwhile, 16 respondents (47.1%) had good self-efficacy in terms of medication adherence. This shows that more than half of the pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center have a

poor level of self-efficacy in carrying out treatment, although there are also some who have good self-efficacy.

- b. Level of compliance with taking medication for pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center

Table 4.6 Level of compliance with taking medication for pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center (n=34)

Compliance	(n)	%
Low	10	29.4
Currently	19	55.9
Obedient	5	14.7
Total	34	100.0

Based on table 4.6, the majority of respondents in this study had a moderate level of compliance, with 19 respondents (55.9%). Meanwhile, 10 respondents (29.4%) had a low level of compliance, and 5 respondents (14.7%) had a good level of compliance. This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center show moderate compliance with treatment, with a small percentage

having low or good compliance.

2. Analisa Bivariat

This bivariate analysis was used to test the hypothesis and to determine the relationship between medication adherence and self-efficacy in pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center. This research uses spermean rank and the results are as shown in the following table:

Table 4.7 Relationship between Adherence to Taking Medication and Self-Efficacy of Pulmonary TB Patients at Community Health Centers Same (n=34)

Self-Efficacy	Compliance			Total	P Value	Rho
	Low	Current	Very good			
Not good	10	8	0	18	.000	.673**
Good	0	11	5	16		
Total	10	19	5	34		

Based on table 4.7, there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and compliance with taking medication for pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center. In the group with poor self-efficacy, 10 respondents showed low compliance, 8 respondents showed moderate compliance, and none showed very good compliance. Meanwhile, in the group with good self-efficacy, no one showed low compliance, 11 respondents showed moderate compliance, and 5 respondents showed good compliance.

A p-value of 0.000 indicates that the relationship between self-efficacy and medication adherence is very statistically significant, so it is unlikely that this result occurred by chance. In addition, the Rho value of 0.673 indicates that the relationship between self-efficacy and adherence to taking medication has quite strong correlation strength. The direction of this relationship is positive, which means that the better a person's self-efficacy, the higher their level of compliance in undergoing pulmonary TB treatment. Conversely, if self-efficacy is low, then adherence to treatment also tends to decrease. This indicates that increasing patient self-efficacy, such as through education and social support, can be an important strategy in increasing medication adherence in pulmonary TB patients.

D. DISCUSSION

1) Respondent Characteristics

a) Age

In the research, it was found that the largest age category of respondents in this study was early adulthood (26-35 years) with 13 respondents (38.2%). Meanwhile, the smallest age category of respondents was seniors (>65 years) with 4 respondents (11.8%). This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center are in the early adult age range, while the elderly age group has the least number of cases.

This is in line with the results of research conducted by Oleh Kesek, (2019) which states that the highest incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) usually occurs in the productive age group, between 15-44 years. The smallest age category in this study was seniors (over 65 years), which only amounted to 4 respondents (11.8%).

This is also relevant to data in previous research, which shows that the number of pulmonary TB patients in the elderly has a lower number when compared to the productive age group. In Indonesia, this age group (elderly) does have a lower prevalence compared to early adulthood or productive

age, who are more susceptible to pulmonary TB infection because they are more frequently exposed to risk factors such as physical activity, work and higher social interactions.

Based on these findings, the authors suggest that increased efforts to prevent and treat pulmonary TB are needed in the productive age group, especially early adults, who are at higher risk due to more intense physical activity, work and social interactions. Health education programs need to focus on this group to increase awareness of risk factors and the importance of early detection. In addition, even though the number of pulmonary TB cases in the elderly group is lower, attention is still needed considering that this group tends to have health conditions that are more susceptible to disease complications. Further research is also recommended to understand the specific factors that contribute to differences in the prevalence of pulmonary TB in various age groups, in order to design prevention strategies that are more effective and appropriate to the needs of the population.

b) Gender

In the research, it was found that the majority of respondents in this study were male, namely 23 respondents (67.6%). Meanwhile, there were 11 female respondents (32.4%). This indicates that cases of pulmonary TB at the Same Community Health Center are more experienced by men than women.

This finding is in line with research conducted by Sunarmi Kurniawaty, (2022), who also found that the majority of pulmonary TB patients were men and had a higher risk of being infected with pulmonary TB. The results of the chi-square test showed a significant relationship between gender and the incidence of pulmonary TB ($p = 0.030 < 0.10$), indicating that men are more susceptible to this infection.

Factors that influence the greater number of male patients in pulmonary TB cases include lifestyle and work patterns. Men are more often exposed to high-risk environments, such as work outside the home, as well as smoking habits which can increase their susceptibility to TB infection. Apart from that, socio-economic factors can also play a role in the high incidence of TB in men.

Based on these findings, the author suggests that more intensive prevention efforts are needed for groups of men who are more susceptible to pulmonary TB, especially through education about healthy lifestyles and the dangers of smoking. In addition, TB screening programs in the work

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environment for men who are often exposed to high risk need to be improved for early detection and faster treatment. Gender-based interventions, such as health campaigns specifically for men, can also help reduce the incidence of pulmonary TB. Furthermore, additional research is needed to explore the socio-economic factors that contribute to the high prevalence of TB in men so that more effective prevention strategies can be designed.

c) Education

In the research, it was found that the largest educational category of respondents in this study was tertiary education (PT), with a total of 14 respondents (41.2%). Meanwhile, the lowest education category was junior high school, with 5 respondents (14.7%). This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center have a higher level of education, namely tertiary education (PT), while the number of patients with junior high school education is relatively smaller.

These findings are in line with research conducted by Marna dkk (2023) which also shows the importance of education in increasing public knowledge about preventing TB disease. This research emphasizes that health education can increase public knowledge, with significant changes in knowledge about TB prevention after being given health education. Before health education, most people had poor knowledge about TB prevention, but after being given education, good knowledge increased significantly.

These results indicate that the level of education can influence an individual's understanding of disease prevention, including pulmonary TB. People with higher levels of education tend to more easily absorb health information and apply it in their daily lives, which can contribute to TB prevention and control.

d) Job

Based on the research results, the majority of respondents in this study were those who worked, with a total of 23 respondents (67.6%). Meanwhile, 11 respondents (32.4%) were unemployed. This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center come from groups who are actively working, while a small portion do not work.

Research conducted by Widiati (2021) regarding the factors of age, level of education, occupation, and the incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis in the work area of the Korleko Community Health Center, East Lombok Regency, it shows that employment is significantly related to the incidence of pulmonary TB. In this study, occupational factors were found to have a significant relationship with the incidence of pulmonary TB ($p = 0.031$). The results of the multivariate analysis showed that work was the most dominant risk factor influencing the incidence of pulmonary TB, with an odds ratio (OR) value of 3.45. This means that respondents who work have a 3.45 times greater chance of experiencing pulmonary TB than those who do not work.

Researchers suggest that more intensive health education is needed for workers to increase awareness in preventing pulmonary TB, as well as routine health screening to detect cases earlier. Policies that support flexibility in working hours for TB patients need to be implemented so that they can undergo optimal treatment. In addition, unemployed patients need social and economic support to increase adherence to treatment. Further research is also needed to identify specific risk factors in the work environment that contribute to the incidence of pulmonary TB.

2) Univariate Analysis

a. Description of the frequency of medication compliance for pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center.

The majority of respondents in this study had poor self-efficacy in medication adherence, with 18 respondents (52.9%). Meanwhile, 16 respondents (47.1%) had good self-efficacy in terms of medication adherence. This shows that more than half of the pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center have a poor level of self-efficacy in carrying out treatment, although there are also some who have good self-efficacy.

Research conducted by Elizah (2024) regarding compliance with taking anti-tuberculosis pulmonary medication at the Surulangun Community Health Center also found that self-efficacy factors play an important role in determining patient compliance in taking TB medication. In this study, self-efficacy, which includes patients' beliefs in their ability to carry out treatment, had a significant relationship with medication adherence. Other factors related to adherence include education, knowledge, attitudes, and family support, all of which play an important role in increasing patient adherence to treatment.

The results of this study show that age is the most dominant factor influencing compliance with taking anti-pulmonary tuberculosis medication, with a p value = 0.001 and an odds ratio (OR) of 10.52. This means that older patients are more likely to adhere to treatment compared to younger patients. Therefore, it is important for health authorities, including at Community Health Centers, to continue to improve education and provide emotional support to patients, especially those who have poor self-efficacy, to ensure the success of treatment and prevent disease transmission.

b. Description of the frequency of self-efficacy of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center

The majority of respondents in this study had a moderate level of compliance, with 19 respondents (55.9%). Meanwhile, 10 respondents (29.4%) had a low level of compliance, and 5 respondents (14.7%) had a very good level of compliance. This shows that the majority of pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center show moderate compliance with treatment, with a

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small percentage having low or very good compliance.

Research by Noranisa (2023) regarding the relationship between self-efficacy and the quality of life of pulmonary TB patients at the Tambang Community Health Center also provides insight into this matter. This research revealed that self-efficacy, namely an individual's belief in their ability to manage their disease, has a significant relationship with the quality of life of pulmonary TB patients. The results showed that 59.7% of patients had low self-efficacy, and 54.7% had poor quality of life. The chi-square test shows a relationship between self-efficacy and the quality of life of pulmonary TB patients (p -value 0.003), which means that patients with low self-efficacy tend to have a poor quality of life.

In the context of adherence to treatment, self-efficacy plays an important role in determining the extent to which patients can commit to following the recommended treatment regimen. Patients with good self-efficacy are more likely to adhere to treatment regularly because they feel they have control over their health and believe that the treatment will bring positive results. Conversely, patients with low self-efficacy may feel less confident or unmotivated to continue undergoing treatment.

3) Bivariate Analysis

This bivariate analysis was used to test the hypothesis and to determine the relationship between medication adherence and self-efficacy in pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center.

There is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and compliance with taking medication for pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center. In the group with poor self-efficacy, 10 respondents showed low compliance, 8 respondents showed moderate compliance, and none showed very good compliance. Meanwhile, in the group with good self-efficacy, no one showed low compliance, 11 respondents showed moderate compliance, and 5 respondents showed very good compliance.

The p value of 0.000 indicates that the relationship between self-efficacy and medication adherence is very statistically significant. The Rho value of 0.673 shows a fairly strong relationship between these two variables. This indicates that the better a person's self-efficacy, the better a person's self-efficacy, the higher their adherence to taking medication..

Similar research conducted by Suaib (2022) at the Bureamaru Community Health Center found something similar, where a p -value of 0.000 indicated a very significant relationship between self-efficacy and adherence to taking medication in TB patients. This research shows that the higher the patient's level of confidence in undergoing treatment, the more likely they are to adhere to the prescribed treatment schedule. This is also supported by other research conducted by Sapeni (2024) at Private Hospital X Bekasi City, which also found a significant relationship between

self-efficacy and adherence to taking medication in TB patients with a p -value of 0.001.

In addition, research conducted by Subandi (2023) at the Putri Ayu Community Health Center, Jambi City showed a fairly strong positive relationship between self-efficacy and compliance with taking medication, with a p -value of 0.005. These findings show that efforts to increase patient self-confidence through educational and supportive approaches can increase their level of adherence to treatment. This research shows that self-efficacy plays an important role in managing TB treatment, which can be obtained through motivation, family support, and a patient empowerment-based approach. Meanwhile, research conducted by Dewi (2022) at Dirgahayu Hospital Samarinda strengthened previous results by finding a significant relationship which also supports the importance of self-efficacy in medication adherence in pulmonary TB patients, with a p -value of 0.000 and a correlation coefficient of 0.518 which shows a fairly strong moderate relationship. All of this research illustrates that patients who feel more confident and confident in their treatment are more likely to adhere to the treatment given, which in turn can increase the success of treatment and speed up the recovery of TB patients.

E. CONCLUSION

The results of the study showed that there was a significant relationship between self-efficacy and compliance with taking medication for pulmonary TB patients at the Same Community Health Center, with a p value of 0.000 which indicated statistical significance. The Rho value of 0.673 shows a strong relationship between these two variables. The better the patient's self-efficacy, the higher their level of compliance in undergoing pulmonary TB treatment.

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